

Incidence of Hyperuricemia Related Backache in Patients among General Population.

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Abstract:

Objective: The main aim of this study was to find the Hyperuricemia related backache in patients among general population.

Place and duration of study: This study was carried out in a duration of 10 months from June 2018 to March 2019 in Medical departments of Jinnah Hospital Lahore.

Materials and Methods: A total of 100 patients were included in this study. Our study included both male and female patients with ages between 12-80 years. Patients which presented in outdoor with lower back pain were included and those with osteomalacia and chronic renal failure were excluded from this study. Informed consent was taken from all the patients and ethical committee approval was taken. A predesigned proforma was used to collect the data. Normal values of uric acid were taken in males as 4-7.0mg/dl and in females as 4-5.7mg/dl. Uric acid levels were checked by blood test which were sent to a reliable laboratory.

Results: A total of 100 patients including both males and females were included in this study with the ages between 12-80 years. Female patients were 54 while male patients were 46. Hyperuricemia was seen in 17 patients. According to age distribution, patients with age less than 40 years were 57 while those with age above 40 years were 43. Hyperuricemia in age group above 40 years was noted in 13 (76.47%) patients and (23.53%) 4 patients in other age group.

Conclusion: Among general population in Pakistan, frequency of Hyperuricemia is much higher and it must be considered seriously in patients with back pain particularly in female patients with higher age who are prone to develop this condition later in life.

Keywords: Backache, Hyperuricemia, females

Introduction: Uric acid produced in the body is mainly excreted by the kidneys and it accounts for almost 70% of all the uric acid produced in the body. Under secretion usually results in Hyperuricemia. Continuous research is being done on the association of lower back pain with increased levels of uric acid in the body (1).

Backache is extremely common in general population of Pakistan and is one of the main reasons of absence from work. Increased levels of uric acid is mainly seen in these patients (8). Data collected in 2007 to 2008 in USA showed that around 8.3 million patients were suffering from Hyperuricemia and the gout caused by it. As it is a chronic disease and long duration is required to treat it, it puts a massive burden economically (6). Backache is one of the commonest problems in Pakistan. This study was carried out to find the incidence of increased uric acid levels in patients with back pain and to give awareness so that better health is provided to the patients.

Materials and Methods: A total of 100 patients were included in this study. Our study included both male and female patients with ages between 12-80 years. Patients which presented in outdoor with lower back pain were included and those with osteomalacia and chronic renal failure were excluded from this study. Informed consent was taken from all the patients and ethical committee approval was taken. A predesigned proforma was used to collect the data. Normal values of uric acid were taken in males as 4-7.0mg/dl and in females as 4-5.7mg/dl. Uric acid levels were checked by blood test which were sent to a reliable laboratory.

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Table1. Age Distribution

		Age distribution		Total
		Male	Female	
		≤ 40 years	> 40 years	
Hyperuricemia	Yes	4 7.0%	13 30.2%	17
	No	53 93.0%	30 69.8%	83
Total		57	43	100

Table 2. Gender distribution

		Age distribution		Total
		Male	Female	
		Yes	No	
Hyperuricemia	Yes	6 13.0%	11 20.4%	17
	No	40 87.0%	43 79.6%	83
Total		46	54	100

Discussion: A lot of studies have been done particularly in females showing correlation between backache and Hyperuricemia (4, 5, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14.).

A study conducted on 36 patients was carried out by Naeema Afzal in sheikh Zaid medical college which showed that 9 (25%) patients had Hyperuricemia. These findings are in correlation with our study which shows 17% of patients with Hyperuricemia (1).

REFERENCES:

1. Afzal N, Mahmud TE, Jahan SS, Kundi S. Uric acid profile in patients with chronic nonspecific musculoskeletal pain. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad*. 2003;15(4):5-9.
2. Lindsey A. MacFarlane, Seoyoung C. Kim Gout: a review of non-modifiable and modifiable risk factors. *Rheum Dis Clin North Am*. 2014; 40(4): 581–4.
3. Ouédraogo DD, Ntsiba H, Tiendrébéogo Zabsonré J, Tiéno H, Bokossa LI, Kaboré F, Drabo J. Clinical spectrum of rheumatologic diseases in a department of rheumatology in Ouagadougou (Burkina Faso). *Clin Rheumatol*. 2014; 33(3):385-9.
4. Winnard D, Wright C, Taylor WJ, Jackson G, Te Karu L, Gow PJ, Arroll B, Thornley S, Gribben B, Dalbeth N. National prevalence of gout derived from administrative health data in Aotearoa New Zealand. *Rheumatology (Oxford)*. 2012;51(5):901-9.
5. Qiliang Liu, Gamble G, Pickering K, Morton S, Dalbeth N. Prevalence and clinical factors associated with gout in patients with diabetes and prediabetes. *Rheumatology (Oxford)*. 2012;51(4):757-59.
6. Grady EP, Carpenter MT, Koenig CD, Older SA, Battafarano DF. Rheumatic findings in Gulf War veterans. *Arch Intern Med*. 1998;158(4):367-71.
7. Hsu HJ, Yen CH, Hsu KH, Wu IW, Lee CC, Hung MJ, Sun CY, Chou CC, Chen YC, Hsieh MF, Chen CY, Hsu CY, Tsai CJ, Wu MS. Factors associated with chronic musculoskeletal pain in patients with chronic kidney disease. *BMC Nephrol*. 2014;15:6.

Hyperuricemia was seen in 26.6% females and 27.1% males in another study which was done by Macfarlane, Seoyoungin and Lindsay in New Zealand. These findings are comparable to our study and the small difference can be due to regional factors.

A large study was done in primary health clinics in Auckland and data of 18358 patients was collected by quilangLiu et al which showed that there were 15.1% (2278/18358) patients suffering from gout due to Hyperuricemia. In our study the results were 17% which is very close to this study (5).

Incidence of only 2.89% of gout was seen in another study done in New Zealand by Wright C and Winnard D et al. The main reason behind this huge difference may be that in their study all the asymptomatic patients were excluded and only the ones with gout were included.

According to our study, sixth patient suffers from Hyperuricemia causing backache so uric acid levels must be checked regularly in all patients.

Conclusion:

Among general population in Pakistan, frequency of Hyperuricemia is much higher and it must be considered seriously in patients with back pain particularly in female patients with higher age who are prone to develop this condition later in life.

8. Roddy E, Choi HK. Epidemiology of Gout. *Rheum Dis Clin North Am.* 2014; 40(2):155–75.
9. Wertheimer A, Morlock R, Becker MA. A Revised Estimate of the Burden of Illness of Gout. *Curr Ther Res Clin Exp.* 2013; 75: 1–4.
10. Maynard JW, McAdams-DeMarco MA, Law A, Kao L, Gelber AC, Coresh J, Baer AN. Racial Differences in Gout Incidence in a Population-Based Cohort: Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities Study. *Am J Epidemiol.* 2014;179(5):576-83.
11. Öztürk MA1, Kaya A, Şenel S, Dönmez S, Balkarlı A, Çobankara V, Erhan Ç, Sayarlıoğlu M, Ugan Y, Tunç ŞE, Pehlivan Y, Kısacık B, Tufan A, Onat AM, Tezcan E, Yıldırım Çetin G, Pamuk ON. Demographic and clinical features of gout patients in Turkey: a multicenter study. *Rheumatol Int.* 2013;33(4):847-52.
12. Chen JH, Yeh WT, Chuang SY, Wu YY, Pan WH. Gender-specific risk factors for incident gout: a prospective cohort study. *Clin Rheumatol.* 2012;31(2):239-45.
13. Gaffo AL, Jacobs DR, Lewis CE, Mikuls TR, Saag KG. Association between being African-American, serum urate levels and the risk of developing hyperuricemia: findings from the Coronary Artery Risk Development in Young Adults cohort. *Arthritis Res Ther.* 2012;14(1): R4
14. Stamp LK, Wells JE, Pitama S, Faatoese A, Doughty RN, Whalley G, Richards AM, Cameron VA. Hyperuricaemia and gout in New Zealand rural and urban Maori and non-Maori communities. *Intern Med J.* 2013;43(6):678-84.